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Efficacy of Different Doses of Pyrethrum on Maize and Bean Grain Weevils under Controlled Conditions

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2.1 Abstract

Grain losses from insect infestation during storage are a serious issue, especially in developing countries, and can result in significant economic losses of several billion dollars and affect food security. Maize and bean weevils are responsible for pre- and post-harvest damage to maize and beans. Currently, farmers have been encouraged to use botanical insecticides for insect pest control instead of synthetic pesticides because of the several problems associated with synthetic substances.

A laboratory study was conducted at the Department of Crop Science and Horticulture Laboratory of Sokoine University of Agriculture in Morogoro, Tanzania, to determine the responses of maize and bean weevils treated with different dosages of pyrethrum and at different times of exposure under controlled conditions. Pyrethrum powder at six dosage levels (0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, and 3.0 g/100g) was mixed with 100 g of disinfested maize and bean grains in 750 ml plastic containers, and the effect on insect mortality, grain damage, and weight loss was assessed.

The results showed that there was significant difference only in the highest concentration (2.0 g/100 g and 2.5 g/100 g for bean and maize grains respectively) pyrethrum and the control ($P < 0.05$). The powders are cheap and safer for human consumption hence is recommended to be used as maize and bean protectants in storage. Further studies on the packaging and sales of these plant powders for easy accessibility to farmers and consumers of maize is also suggested.

Keywords: Maize grains; bean grains; chemical control; pyrethrum powder; pyrethrum extracts; maize weevils; bean weevil

2.2 Introduction

Grain losses due to insect invasion throughout storage are serious problems, particularly in developing countries, leading to major economic losses (Dubey *et al.*, 2008; Oni and Ileke 2008; Talukder *et al.*, 2004). Insects can damage crops by accumulating exuviae, webbing, and dead animals, in addition to directly devouring grains. High insect debris concentrations could result in grain that is unfit for human consumption

December 31, 2024

and a reduction in food commodities in terms of both quality and quantity. Insect infestations may alter the storage environment, creating "hotspots" of warmth and humidity that encourage storage fungus and increase losses (Yallappa *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, the use of synthetic insecticides has been essential for the control of these insect pests, even though many of these substances have serious drawbacks, including the risk of user contamination, food residues, insect pest resurgence and resistance, lethal effects on non-target organisms, and environmental pollution (Taponjou *et al.*, 2002). Due to the drawbacks in the usage of synthetic insecticides, botanical insecticides have been promoted instead since it is thought that they are safer for the environment, typically less expensive, and simple for farmers and small industries to handle and apply (Belmain *et al.*, 2001; Habib *et al.*, 2011). Also, it is thought that tropical areas possess a number of plant species with insecticidal qualities (Ileke and Oni, 2011; Saxena *et al.*, 1992; Shaala *et al.*, 2005). This study aims to reveal the effectiveness of different doses of pyrethrum on maize and bean grain weevils under controlled conditions (laboratory conditions) and times of exposure.

2.3 Materials and Methods

2.3.1 Study area

The experimental study was conducted at Sokoine University of Agriculture (SUA), Morogoro, Tanzania, in the Horticulture Unit Laboratory under the College of Agriculture in the Department of Crop Science and Horticulture (S06° 56'04.00'', E037° 32'50.8'', and 515 m.a.s.l.) from November 2020 to May 2021 in the Morogoro region of Tanzania.

2.3.2 Materials

2.3.2.1 Plant materials

The flowers of a local variety of pyrethrum were collected from TARI-Uyole, Mbeya region. The samples were dried for 7 days under shade to avoid thermal and photo-decomposition of the active ingredients. Then, the dried flowers were ground with a micro plant grinding machine and sieved through a 0.25 mm pore-size mesh sieve to obtain uniform fine dust particles, as described by Araya and Eman (2009) and Jembere *et al.* (2005).

2.3.2.2 Grains materials (maize and beans)

The maize grains (Staha) and bean grains (Kablankeji) were bought from smallholder farmers. They were sufficiently dried to have a moisture content of 15%. The grains were disinfested by keeping them in a deep freezer at a temperature of -1 °C for 48 hours. This harvested maize and beans had no history of insecticide treatment.

2.3.2.3 Insect collection and rearing

Maize and bean weevils were isolated from infested maize and bean grain collected from farmers' stores in the Morogoro region. The insects were reared at an optimum temperature and humidity of 27 °C and 70% relative humidity for *S. zeamais* and 28–30 °C and 70% RH for bean weevils in two separate Kilner jars containing 2 kg of undamaged maize and bean grains. The jars were covered with perforated lids for aeration and to prevent the escape of the insects. The insect colonies were retained for two months (60 days) in order to obtain enough insects for the experiments.

2.3.3 Methods

2.3.3.1 Experimental protocol

In clean and dry bottles, 100 g of disinfested grains were placed. The bottles that were used for the experiment were heat sterilised in an autoclave at 60 °C for three hours to kill any insects and fungal spores that might have been housed inside as well as outside the bottles. Pyrethrum powder was applied at a rate of 0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5%, 2.0%, 2.5%, and 3.0% (w/w). The powders were thoroughly mixed with the grains for five minutes with the aid of a glass rod to ensure thorough admixture. For synthetic insecticide, Actellic Super Dust was used at the recommended rate as a standard check, and for comparison, an untreated check was also included. Forty

December 31, 2024

similar-aged maize bean weevils were introduced into each bottle, which was then covered with perforated lids to avoid weevils escaping and allow aeration. Then bottles were placed at a temperature of $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $70 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity (Tadele *et al.*, 2010).

2.4 Experimental Design

The completely randomized design (CRD) was used to set up the treatments, and four replications of each treatment were made.

2.5 Data Collection

Data collected included the number of dead and live insects, the number of damaged and undamaged maize grains, and the weight of damaged and undamaged grains at an interval of 7 days for 42 days (i.e., 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, and 42 days).

The percentage mortality, weight losses, and percentage of damaged grains were also calculated using the following formula:

1. Percentage mortality (FAO, 1988)

$$\text{Mortality (\%)} = \frac{Nd}{Ti} \times 100$$

Where; Nd = Number of dead insects and Ti = Total number of insect

2. Percentage damage (%D)

$$\text{Grain Damage (\%)} = \frac{Nd}{TNG} \times 100$$

Where: Nd = number of damaged grains and TNG : total number of grains

3. Efficacy of treatment (El-Ghar *et al.*, 1987)

$$\text{Protection (\%)} = \frac{TF1PC - TF1PT}{TF1PC} \times 100$$

Where; $TF1PC$: total F1 progeny in control and $TF1PT$: total F1 progeny in treatment

4. Percentage weight loss (Adams and Schulten, 1978).

$$\text{Weight Loss (\%)} = \frac{\{(Wu \times Nd) - (Wd \times Nu)\}}{Wu \times (Nd + Nu)} \times 100$$

Where: WL = Weight loss, Wu = Weight of undamaged grain, Nu = Number of undamaged grain, Wd = Weight of damaged grain, and Nd = Number of damaged grain.

2.6 Statistical Analysis

Collected data on the number of live and dead insects and also the percentage mortality was organized using Microsoft Excel and subjected to an analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Gen Stat Discovery Edition

15 (VSN International, UK) at a significance level of 5%. The mean separation was done using the Duncan Multiple Range Test. A Statistical Model for Completely Randomized Design (CRD)

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + \tau_i + \epsilon_{ij}$$

Where; μ = grand mean, τ_i = deviations from the grand mean and ϵ_{ij} = error terms.

December 31, 2024

2.7 Results

2.7.1 Percentage mortality of weevils

2.7.1.1 Bean weevils

Results demonstrated effects on the percentage of weevil mortality, which increased with the amount of powder used, and significant differences ($P < 0.05$) across treatments at all dosages tested for their insecticidal activity (Fig. 2.1). Among treatment doses, the highest percentage mortality was recorded for treatment doses, i.e., 2.0, 2.5, and 3.0 g/100 g, at 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, and 42 days after treatment, and the lowest percentage mortality of 0% was observed from untreated treatment at 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, and 42 days after treatment. 2.0 g/100 g of pyrethrum dose was not significantly different from 2.5 and 3.0 g/100 g pyrethrum doses and those of synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust).

Figure 2.1: Percentage mortality of bean weevils at different doses

2.7.1.2 Maize weevils

The results on the percentage of mortality showed very significant variations ($P < 0.05$) between the therapy doses used (Fig. 2.2 and 2.3). The highest percentage of mortality among treatment doses was noted for treatment doses of 2.5 and 3.0 g/100 g at 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, and 42 days, whereas the lowest percentage of mortality of 0% was noted for untreated treatment at 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, and 42 days following treatment (Figs. 2.2 and 2.3). Pyrethrum doses of 2.5 g/100 g and 3.0 g/100 g, as well as those of synthetic insecticides, were not statistically different from one another (Actellic Super Dust).

Figure 2.2: Percentage mortality of maize weevils at different doses

Figure 2.3: Comparison between the percentage mortality of bean and maize weevils at different doses

2.7.2 Grains damage and time of exposures

2.7.2.1 Bean grains

The results on percentage damage revealed very highly significant differences ($P < 0.05$) among the treatment doses applied (Table 2.1).

Among treatment doses, the highest percentage of grain damage was recorded in the untreated at 42 days after treatment, while the lowest percentage of weight loss was observed from treatment with high doses, i.e., 2.5 and 3 g/100 g, at 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, and 42 days after treatment. It was also observed for synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust) (Table 2.1). 2.0 g/100 g of pyrethrum dose was not significantly different from 2.5 and 3.0 g/100 g of pyrethrum dose and those of synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust).

Table 2.1: Percentage damage of bean grains due to bean weevils

Treatments (g/100g)	Grain damage (%)					
	7 Days	14 Days	21 Days	28 Days	35 Days	42 Days
Control (-)	11.00 a	20.00 a	37.00 a	50.00 a	68.50 a	71.50 a

December 31, 2024

0.5	7.25 b	10.50 b	19.00 b	31.50 b	50.00 b	52.50 b
1.0	3.50 c	7.25 c	9.00 c	18.25 c	18.25 c	19.25 c
1.5	1.50 d	4.25 d	6.25 d	8.50 d	8.50 d	8.50 d
2.0	0.50 e	0.50 e	0.50 e	0.50 e	0.50 e	0.50 e
2.5	0.00 e	0.00 e	0.00 e	0.00 e	0.00 e	0.00 e
3.0	0.00 e	0.00 e	0.00 e	0.00 e	0.00 e	0.00 e
Control(+)	0.00 e	0.00 e	0.00 e	0.00 e	0.00 e	0.00 e
Grand Mean	2.969	5.31	8.969	13.59	18.22	19.03
LSD	0.7108	1.195	0.7461	1.432	1.386	1.048
CV%	16.3	15.3	5.7	7.2	5.2	3.7
F. Probability	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

Means followed by the same letter(s) in the same columns are not significantly different according to DMRT ($P<0.05$) Control (-) and Control (+), untreated and treated with synthetic insecticides (Actellic super dust) at the recommended rate.

2.7.2.2 Maize grains

The results on percentage damage show very highly significant differences ($P<0.05$) amongst the treatment doses applied (Table 2.2). Among treatment doses, the highest percentage of grain damage was recorded in the untreated at 42 days, while the lowest percentage of weight loss was observed from treatment with high doses, i.e., 3.0 g/100 g at 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, and 42 days. It was also observed for synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust) (Table 2.2). 2.5 g/100 g of pyrethrum dose was not significantly different from 3.0 g/100 g of pyrethrum dose and those of chemical insecticides (Actellic Super Dust).

Table 2.2: Percentage damage of maize grains due to maize weevils

Treatments (g/100g)	Grain damage (%)					
	7 Days	14 Days	21 Days	28 Days	35 Days	42 Days
Control (-)	6.25 a	14.75 a	29.00 a	43.50 a	62.50 a	78.75 a
0.5	2.50 b	5.25 b	14.00 b	31.25 b	42.25 b	50.75 b
1.0	2.25 b	4.25 c	8.00 c	14.00 c	31.75 c	35.00 c
1.5	1.25 c	2.25 d	3.50 d	8.50 d	24.25 d	34.50 c
2.0	1.00 c	1.50 d	1.50 e	2.25 e	9.75 e	11.25 d
2.5	0.25 d	0.25 e	0.25 f	0.25 f	0.25 f	0.25 e
3.0	0.00 d	0.00 e	0.00 f	0.00 f	0.00 f	0.00 e
Control(+)	0.00 d	0.00 e	0.00 f	0.00 f	0.00 f	0.00 e
Grand Mean	1.688	3.53	7.03	12.47	21.34	26.31
LSD	0.611	0.873	1.249	1.777	1.395	1.492
CV%	24.6	16.8	12.1	9.7	4.4	3.9
F. Probability	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

Means followed by the same letter(s) in the same columns are not significantly different according to DMRT ($P<0.05$).

Control (-) and Control (+), untreated and treated with synthetic insecticides (Actellic super dust) at the recommended rate.

2.7.3 Grains weight losses and time of exposures

2.7.3.1 Bean grains

Results on the percentage of weight loss showed highly significant differences ($P<0.05$) between the treatment doses used (Fig. 2.4). The untreated grains were observed to have the greatest weight loss percentage among treatment doses at 42 days after treatment, but treatment with high doses, i.e., 2.5 and 3 g/100 g, was associated

December 31, 2024

with the lowest weight loss percentage at 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, and 42 days following treatment. Artificial insecticides (Actellic Super Dust) were also discovered (Fig. 2.4). Pyrethrum dosages of 2.0 g/100 g, 2.5 g/100 g, and 3.0 g/100 g, as well as those of synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust), were not noticeably different from one another.

Figure 2.4: Percentage weight loss of bean grains at different doses

2.7.3.2 Maize grains

The results on the percentage of weight loss revealed highly significant differences ($P < 0.05$) among the treatment doses applied (Fig. 2.5). Among treatment doses, the highest percentage of weight loss was recorded in the untreated at 42 days after treatment, while the lowest percentage of weight loss was observed from treatment with high doses, i.e., 3.0 g/100 g, at 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, and 42 days. It was also observed for synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust) (Table 3.6). 2.5 g/100 g of pyrethrum dose was not significantly different from 3.0 g/100 g of pyrethrum dose and those of synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust).

December 31, 2024

Figure 2.5: Percentage weight loss of bean grains at different doses**2.8 Discussion**

The study on the efficacy of pyrethrum powders and a synthetic insecticide, actelic super dust, showed that both the botanicals and the synthetic insecticide are good protectants of maize (*Zea mays*) and beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) against maize and bean weevils. The mortality rates of maize and bean weevils were quite high (100%) with the different regimens of treatments. The highest mortality rate of maize and bean weevils (100%) with actelic super dust was recorded at the recommended rate. This agrees with the work of Ukpai *et al.* (2017) and Amadi *et al.* (2018), who reported that higher dosages of treatment worked effectively in the control of *Sitophilus zeamais*. All levels of the botanicals used in this study showed some insecticidal properties by significantly reducing the number of maize and bean weevils in the experimental vials. The results lend credence to the fact that pyrethrum flower powders can be used to control the infestation of maize and bean weevils in stored maize and bean grains. The utilisation of different plant products as stored product protectants has been reported by Mulungu *et al.* (2007), Law-Ogbomo and Enobakhare (2007), Araya and Eman (2009), and Amadi *et al.* (2018). This shows that resource-poor farmers and maize and bean grain dealers can use plant powders to control maize and bean weevils. A higher concentration of pyrethrum flower powder recorded the highest mortality than the low concentration; the flower powder of pyrethrum was toxic to the weevils. This highest mortality rate was recorded in 2.5 g of beans and 3.0 g of maize. This result is similar to the work of Omotoso (2014), where a higher dose of plant powder has been reported to work effectively in the control of stored grains. This shows that pyrethrum is a good protector of maize and bean grains against maize and bean weevils. Shiberi and Negeri (2014) reported that pyrethrum is a good protectant of stored maize and bean grains against weevil infestation. Pyrethrum showed some insecticidal properties in the protection of the maize and bean grain against maize and bean weevils; the high doses recorded higher mortality than the low doses. The highest mortality was recorded in the treatment with 2.5 and 3.0 g/kg of bean and maize weevils, respectively. The use of the plant powders could have resulted in the death of insects as a result of the physical barrier effects of the plant materials (Muzemu *et al.*, 2013). This is because the powder has the tendency to block the spiracles of the insects thus impairing respiration and leading to the death of insects. While feeding on whole grains, maize and bean weevils can pick up lethal doses of the treatment thus resulting in stomach poisoning (Law-Ogbomo and Enobakhare, 2007) and subsequent death. Maize and bean weevils treated with actelic super dust had the highest weevil mortality (100%) compared to the other treatments. However, the difference in effectiveness was not significant in high doses but significant in low doses.

2.9 Conclusion

The findings of this work indicate that pyrethrum powder could be used to control the maize and bean weevils in stored maize and bean grains, respectively. This will reduce chemical insecticide usage, remove the risks of toxic residues in foods, and ensure the continued availability of insect-free maize and beans for food, planting, trading, and storage. It is recommended that the application of 3.0g of pyrethrum powder per 100g of maize be used for complete mortality of the maize weevil, while the application of 2.5g of pyrethrum powder per 100g of bean be used for complete mortality of the bean weevil. Also, the application of 3.0g of pyrethrum powder to 100g of stored maize and 2.5 g of pyrethrum powder to 100g of stored beans will significantly reduce the natality and oviposition of maize and bean weevils. Further studies aimed at determining the active ingredients (pyrethrins) of pyrethrum are recommended. Furthermore, the active ingredient should be formulated into a bioinsecticide for the management of maize and bean storage weevils.

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December 31, 2024

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December 31, 2024

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